

Improved photocatalytic water splitting activity of highly porous WO₃ photoanodes by electrochemical H⁺ intercalation

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The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest

Author contribution statement

The synthesis of the films, their SEM surface morphology and photoelectrochemical characterizations were performed by RL, under the supervision of NT and HC. The XPS structural characterization and modelling was performed by TM. Writing and original draft preparation by RL. Review and editing performed by RL, NT, and HC.

Keywords

Intensity modulated photocurrent spectroscopy, Hydrogen intercalation, Tungsten oxide thin films, Anodization and photo-catalytic properties, Photocatalytic water splitting

Abstract

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WO₃ photoanodes are widely used in photoelectrochemical catalysis, but as regular the as-synthesized material is annealed before application. It is therefore desirable to explore less energy-intensive treatments. In this study, WO₃ films of up to 3.9 μm thickness were obtained by galvanostatic anodization in a neutral-pH Na₂SO₄ and NaF electrolyte, also containing a NaH₂PO₂ additive (to suppress O₂ accumulation on the pore walls). Additionally, the WO₃ photoanodes were modified by applying a cathodic reduction (H⁺ intercalation) and anodic activation treatment in-situ. XPS spectra revealed that intercalation modifies WO₃ films; the amount of W⁵⁺-O and O-vacancy bonds was increased. Furthermore, subsequent activation leads to a decrease of the W⁵⁺ signal, but the amount of O-vacancy bonds remains elevated. The as-prepared and reduced (intercalated & activated) films were tested as OER photoanodes in acidic 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ media, under illumination with a 365 nm wavelength LED. It was observed that thinner films generated larger photocurrents. The peculiarities detected by XPS for reduced films correlate well with their improved photocatalytic activity. Photo-electrochemical impedance and intensity modulated photocurrent spectroscopies were combined with steady-state measurements in order to elucidate the effects of H⁺ intercalation on photoelectrochemical performance. The reduction results in films with enhanced photoexcited charge carrier generation/separation, improved conductivity, and possibly even suppressed bulk recombination. Thus, the intercalation & activation adopted in this study can be reliably used to improve the overall activity of as-synthesized WO₃ photoanodes, and particularly of those that are initially poorly photoactive.

Contribution to the field

Electrochemically synthesized (e.g. by anodization) tungsten (III) oxide films have been and are still being widely investigated for their various electro-/photocatalytic, electrochromic, semiconductor properties. When employed as photoanodes for OER, the as-synthesized films are often annealed at high temperatures to impart a degree of crystallinity, which typically results in enhanced photocatalytic properties due to improved conductivity, decreased number of defect/trap sites, etc. However, less energy-intensive modification methods may be used. In this study the natural affinity of tungsten (III) oxide to incorporate protons into its lattice is exploited in order to improve the material's photocatalytic OER activity. An in-situ cathodic reduction (proton intercalation) step is applied to form a metallically conductive HxWO₃ material. An activation step is then carried out under normal operating conditions; XPS measurements reveal that these processes naturally tune the number of W (V) and W (VI) oxide, as well as O-vacancy bonds. It is revealed that this treatment is particularly effective in activating thick and otherwise poorly conductive/photocatalytically active tungsten oxide films. This is an interesting result, as current literature on the effect of proton intercalation on the photocatalytic OER activity of tungsten (III) oxide films is still inconclusive.

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In review

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In review

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11 **Keywords: tungsten oxide, anodization, photocatalytic water splitting, hydrogen intercalation,**
12 **intensity modulated photocurrent spectroscopy.**

13 **Abstract**

14 WO₃ photoanodes are widely used in photoelectrochemical catalysis, but typically the as-synthesized
15 material is annealed before application. It is therefore desirable to explore less energy-intensive
16 treatments. In this study, WO₃ films of up to 3.9 μm thickness were obtained by galvanostatic
17 anodization of tungsten foil in a neutral-pH Na₂SO₄ and NaF electrolyte, also containing a NaH₂PO₂
18 additive (to suppress O₂ accumulation on the pore walls). Additionally, the WO₃ photoanodes were
19 modified by applying a cathodic reduction (H⁺ intercalation) and anodic activation treatment *in-situ*.
20 XPS spectra revealed that intercalation modifies WO₃ films; the amount of W⁵⁺-O and O-vacancy
21 bonds was increased. Furthermore, subsequent activation leads to a decrease of the W⁵⁺ signal, but
22 the amount of O-vacancy bonds remains elevated. The as-prepared and reduced (intercalated &
23 activated) films were tested as OER photoanodes in acidic 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ media, under illumination
24 with a 365 nm wavelength LED. It was observed that thinner films generated larger photocurrents.
25 The peculiarities detected by XPS for reduced films correlate well with their improved photocatalytic
26 activity. Photo-electrochemical impedance and intensity modulated photocurrent spectroscopies were
27 combined with steady-state measurements in order to elucidate the effects of H⁺ intercalation on
28 photoelectrochemical performance. The reduction results in films with enhanced photoexcited charge
29 carrier generation/separation, improved conductivity, and possibly even suppressed bulk
30 recombination. Thus, the intercalation & activation adopted in this study can be reliably used to
31 improve the overall activity of as-synthesized WO₃ photoanodes, and particularly of those that are
32 initially poorly photoactive.

33

34 **1 Introduction**

35 Oxide materials have long been thought to be the most promising photo-electrodes, as their corrosion
36 resistance should ensure stable performance over long periods of time (Bak et al., 2002). Due to their
37 natural abundance and recently-discovered versatility, transition metal oxides have been the subject
38 of extensive research as electro- and photocatalysts for many applications (oxygen/hydrogen
39 evolution, CO₂ reduction, oxidation of organic compounds and alcohols, etc. (Huang et al., 2015; Wu
40 et al., 2019)). Tungsten oxide (VI) in particular has garnered substantial attention. It is an n-type
41 semiconductor, and has a narrow band gap, typically reported within the range of 2.5 – 2.8 eV,
42 although as measured by indirect optical transitions up to 3.38 eV for amorphous films (Patel et al.,
43 2009; Gullapalli et al., 2010). Thus, part of the visible light range (~ < 450 nm) can be utilized for
44 WO₃ films. However, the band gap and other electrical parameters such as conductivity of WO₃ films
45 can vary greatly with their microstructure, grain size, phase, and crystallinity (Gullapalli et al., 2010;
46 Vemuri et al., 2010). It is therefore evident that the catalytic properties of given films will critically
47 depend on their synthesis technique.

48 Films, layers, and coatings of WO₃ can be obtained in many different ways: sol-gel and hydrothermal
49 syntheses, physical vapor deposition, electrochemical deposition, templating, and other methods that
50 have been extensively covered by numerous review articles (Zheng et al., 2011; Liu et al., 2012;
51 Mardare and Hassel, 2019; Dong et al., 2020). In this study, the attention will be directed towards
52 electrochemical methods of WO₃ synthesis, which can be distinguished into electrodeposition and
53 anodization. Cathodic electrodeposition typically proceeds through a peroxotungstic acid precursor.
54 The main benefit of this method is the ability to deposit WO₃ onto various conductive substrates to
55 form electrochromic devices (Lin et al., 2016). Catalytically active nanostructured films can also be
56 obtained (Kwong et al., 2012; Ali et al., 2014; Santos et al., 2015). In contrast, anodization requires
57 the use of metallic tungsten as a substrate. Upon application of a sufficient potential in corrosive
58 media, the metal dissolves into a WO₂²⁺ complex, and through a heptavalent intermediate (W₂O₅)
59 turns into WO₃ (Qi et al., 2014). This process can occur under potentiostatic or galvanostatic modes.
60 The film's thickness under potentiostatic conditions depends linearly on the applied potential
61 (strength of the applied electric field), and a better-defined porous morphology depending on the
62 electrolyte is obtained under intermediate applied voltage e.g. 50 V (Lai and Sreekantan, 2013; Syrek
63 et al., 2018). On the other hand, galvanostatic anodization may be considered when it is desirable to
64 control the rate of the occurring electrochemical processes (Casado et al., 2019), and may result in
65 increased growth rate of the oxide film (Manovah David et al., 2014). It is known that under
66 galvanostatic conditions the voltage reaches a peak, and the following drop indicates pore formation
67 by field-induced oxide dissolution (Parkhutik and Shershulsky, 1992; Mukherjee et al., 2003).

68 Moreover, the morphological, structural, and even photocatalytic properties of WO₃ films can be
69 improved with the use of certain additives/complexing agents during anodization (Fernández-
70 Domene et al., 2017). Fluoride is widely used, and it is known to increase the rate of dissolution of
71 the W₂O₅ intermediate and WO₃, which typically has an effect on the morphology of the pores
72 (Karastoyanov and Bojinov, 2008; Zych et al., 2020).

73 Further enhancement of the WO₃ films' catalytic activity can be achieved through intercalation and
74 doping. As-anodized WO₃ films are sometimes referred to as “bleached”, whereas after reductive
75 intercalation they become “colored”, owing to the dark blue appearance of hydrogen tungsten bronze
76 H_xWO₃ (Patel et al., 2010; Ou et al., 2012). This process is reversible, and at anodic potentials the
77 film will become bleached again after the protons de-intercalate. In fact, it had been reported that a
78 larger number of color-bleach cycles can even change the microstructure and porosity of the WO₃ as
79 the penetration of water into the film causes expansion of the lattice (Reichman and Bard, 1979). A
80 study on the effect of protonation on the photocatalytic water splitting properties of a CVD-formed

81 WO₃ film found that protonated films exhibited poorer photoelectrochemical activity (Calero et al.,
 82 2016). However, a highly beneficial outcome of cathodic reduction was observed on differently-
 83 prepared WO₃ nanoflakes; a five-fold increase in photocurrent was observed after reduction, and this
 84 effect was ascribed to a similar increase in donor density as measured by the Mott-Schottky method
 85 (Yu et al., 2017). It has been hypothesized that due to the interaction of conduction and valence
 86 bands of semiconducting WO₃ and metallic H_xWO₃, the photogenerated electron-hole recombination
 87 is suppressed and the life-time of photogenerated holes consequently increases, resulting in a higher
 88 charge separation efficiency (Zhang et al., 2015). Photoelectrochemical analysis suggests that
 89 electrochemical doping of WO₃ with H⁺ passivates surface trap states, thus reducing recombination
 90 and improving the charge separation efficiency (Liu et al., 2016). Moreover, non-electrochemical
 91 methods such as substitutional cation doping, thermal oxygen vacancy engineering, and chemical
 92 reduction have been shown to have similar effects on the structure and catalytic properties of
 93 modified WO₃ photoanodes (Solarska et al., 2010; Li et al., 2017; Hu et al., 2021).

94 The target of this study was the synthesis of highly porous tungsten oxide films by galvanostatic
 95 anodization and evaluation of their photoelectrochemical water splitting performance as as-deposited
 96 and reduced WO₃ photoanodes. Non-stationary methods such as photo-electrochemical impedance
 97 spectroscopy and intensity modulated photocurrent spectroscopy were used to discern conductivity
 98 and space-charge layer effects on the oxygen evolution reaction.

99

100 2 Materials and methods

101 2.1 Anodization procedure and treatment of WO₃ films

102 The films investigated in this study were prepared by anodizing tungsten foil (99.5% Alfa Aesar, 0.1
 103 mm thick). The foils were shaped to have a working area of 1x1 cm dimensions, and during
 104 anodization both sides of the foil were in contact with the electrolyte (2 cm² surface area). Before
 105 anodization, the substrates were degreased in 2-propanol, cleaned in a NaOH solution to remove
 106 residual oxides, and rinsed well with distilled water. The anodization was carried out in a two-
 107 electrode cell using a magnetic stirrer. The anode was tungsten foil, and the cathode was a stainless-
 108 steel coil. A high-voltage power supply unit (Consort EV245) was used, and galvanostatic conditions
 109 were chosen. The electrolyte with the following composition: 1 M Na₂SO₄, 75 mM NaF, 0.1 M
 110 NaH₂PO₂, at pH 8 was used for anodization. Eqs. 1-3 describe the anodic formation of a WO₃ film
 111 under these conditions. Mechanistically the growth of a WO₃ film occurs by transfer of oxygen
 112 vacancies from the metal/film interface, across the oxide film, and to the film/solution interface, as
 113 described by the point defect model (Macdonald et al., 1992).

114 Meanwhile, although WO₃ is thermodynamically stable in acidic solutions, electrical-field-induced
 115 film dissolution is known to occur, and can be summed up by eqs. 4 and 5 (without and with F⁻
 116 respectively):

117 Sodium hypophosphite was added as it prevents accumulation of excess oxygen on the pore walls
118 during anodization (Zhu et al., 2008; Cao et al., 2020), also it can affect the growth mechanism of the
119 film by reducing some of the components (Yang et al., 2006; Gan et al., 2012; Chu et al., 2014).
120 Moreover, the photocatalytic activity of WO_3 films obtained without hypophosphite was inferior as
121 our preliminary experiments showed. A galvanostatic current density of 25 mA cm^{-2} and anodization
122 times from 2 to 30 minutes (**Table 1**) were chosen in order to obtain films with different thickness.
123 The as-anodized films were washed well with distilled water and dried with a heat gun.

124 In order to improve the photoelectrochemical properties of the WO_3 films, a cathodic reduction step
125 was performed *in-situ* (0.1 M Na_2SO_4 adjusted to pH 2 with sulfuric acid) before photocatalytic
126 measurements. The reduction was carried out by applying a potential of -0.5 V (vs. Ag/AgCl) for 300
127 s. Before characterization, the reduced WO_3 (*r-WO₃*) were activated by applying constant
128 illumination of 50 mW cm^{-2} under potentiostatic conditions (1.2 V vs. Ag/AgCl) for 3000 seconds
129 (**Table 1**). This activation step allowed for the background re-oxidation current to subside and
130 ensured that the measured photocurrent can be confidently attributed to just photocatalytic oxygen
131 evolution.

132 [TABLE 1]

133 2.2 Morphology and composition

134 A dual beam system Helios Nanolab 650 with an energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectrometer INCA
135 Energy 350 and X-Max 20 mm^2 detector was used for the study of surface morphology. For focused
136 ion beam (FIB) analysis, a Ga^+ ion beam was used to create precise channels for cross sections on a
137 sample surface.

138 The XPS analyses were carried out with a Kratos Axis Supra spectrometer using a monochromatic Al
139 K(alpha) source (25 mA, 15 kV). The Kratos charge neutralizer system was used on all specimens.
140 Survey scan analyses were carried out with an analysis area of 300×700 microns and a pass energy
141 of 160 eV. High resolution analyses were carried out with an analysis area of 300×700 microns and
142 a pass energy of 20 eV. The XPS signal due to adventitious carbon located at 284.8 eV was used as a
143 binding energy (BE) reference.

144 2.3 Photoelectrochemical characterization

145 The WO_3 films were tested for their photoelectrochemical activity under illumination by a 365 nm
146 UV LED of variable light intensity. All (photo)electrochemical experiments were carried out using
147 an Autolab PGSTAT 302N equipped with a FRA32 module and an LED driver. The light intensity of
148 50 mW cm^{-2} was chosen with the expectation that a more intense I_0 would generally yield a stronger
149 photocurrent signal that is easier distinguishable from background noise. The linear sweep
150 voltammetry (LSV), chronoamperometric, photo-electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (PEIS),
151 and intensity modulated photocurrent spectroscopy (IMPS) responses were measured in a quartz
152 three-electrode cell with an $\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}/\text{sat. KCl}$ reference electrode. Unless specified otherwise, all
153 potentials were referenced against this electrode and represented as vs. Ag/AgCl . The back side of
154 the photoanodes was insulated, leaving a 1 cm^2 working front-facing surface area in contact with the
155 electrolyte, and front-illumination was used. All measurements were carried out in 0.1 M Na_2SO_4 ,
156 adjusted to a pH of 2 with sulfuric acid, to ensure better electrochemical stability of tungsten oxide.
157 Incident photon conversion efficiencies were calculated based on eq. 6.

$$IPCE(\%) = \frac{j_{ss}(mA\ cm^{-2}) * 1240 (V\ nm)}{I_0(mW\ cm^{-2}) * \lambda (nm)} * 100 \quad (6)$$

158 PEIS and IMPS spectra were obtained in the 10 kHz – 0.1 Hz frequency range, with an amplitude
 159 10% of potential or light intensity respectively, at applied potentials from 0.4 V to 2.0 V. It was
 160 ensured that the conditions of causality, linearity, and stability are met, and the spectra were verified
 161 with the Kramers-Kronig transform procedure to ensure adequate validity. The spectra were fitted
 162 with equivalent electric circuits (EEC) using the Zview software. It was taken care that the discrete
 163 elements of the circuit had a physical meaning in the corresponding system, and that, as much as
 164 possible, the mathematical fitting errors should not exceed 10 %. A typical characterization
 165 procedure for WO₃ film was: (1) OCP determination for 60 seconds; (2) LSV from 0.4 V to 2.0 V at
 166 2 mV s⁻¹ with chopped UV *on/off* (10 s ON / 10 s OFF) light; (3) PEIS measurements at potentials
 167 from 0.4 V to 2.0 V; (4) potentiostatic 30 second UV *on/off* pulses at 1.2 V; (5) IMPS spectra
 168 measurement at potentials from 0.4 V to 2.0 V;

169 3 Results and discussion

170 3.1 Structural and photoelectrochemical evaluation

171 SEM images of the surface of as-anodized WO₃ films show high porosity in all studied cases (**Fig. 1**
 172 **(A-C)**). Prolonging the anodization time results in larger and more disordered macrostructures of the
 173 WO₃ film, along with propagation of cracks. Cross-sections obtained by FIB analysis reveal that the
 174 porous structure extends till the substrate (**Fig. 1 (D-F)**). Moreover, the average thickness of the
 175 investigated samples is linearly dependent on time. The film that was obtained by anodizing for 2
 176 minutes is relatively compact (**Fig. 1 D**), but still porous with rather uneven thickness in different
 177 points (from 591 to 856 nm). Prolonging the anodization to 5 minutes resulted in the formation of a
 178 thicker film (**Fig. 1E**) of similar porosity and a rougher surface. The pores within this film tend to
 179 expand horizontally rather than vertically, forming large empty gaps in the material, which may
 180 hinder charge transfer and result in lower photocurrents for as-anodized films. Finally, the film
 181 obtained after anodization for 30 minutes is very thick (**Fig. 1F**) and highly porous. The propagation
 182 of horizontal channels is particularly clear for this film. Here, it should be noted that the surface
 183 morphologies of as-anodized films after reduction and activation processes do not change.

184 [FIGURE 1]

185 The preliminary experiment performed on the WO₃ films was linear sweep voltammetry with a
 186 chopped on/off UV illumination pulse. The potential (*E*) was scanned from 0.4 V up to a cut-off
 187 condition of 2 V at 2 mV s⁻¹ (**Fig. 1 (G-I)**). At the onset near OCP only a small photocurrent (*j_{ph}*) up
 188 to ~ 10 μA cm⁻² was observed for all films, but afterwards *j_{ph}* rapidly grew with increasing applied
 189 potential. Here the background current (which can be inferred from the “UV off” parts of the
 190 polarization curves) was not corrected for, but it was on the level of a few μA cm⁻² throughout the
 191 experimental potential range, so the entire measured current is attributed to photocurrent. This
 192 relation between *j_{ph}* – *E* is expected, because as the strength of the electric field is increased, the
 193 space-charge layer within the semiconductor also broadens, which allows more photogenerated
 194 charge carriers to participate in the circuit. Note, that the r-WO₃ LSV curves shown here were
 195 registered after a 3000 s equilibration step, during which the re-oxidation current settled at a near-
 196 zero value.

197 The j_{ph} may be expected to plateau when either: (a) the space charge layer becomes of similar
 198 dimension as the penetration depth of incident light, or (b) diffusion limitations begin hindering
 199 charge transfer. This phenomenon does not occur at least until 2.0 V showing that the films have a
 200 rather large operating potential range. LSV measurements demonstrate that thinner (2min- and 5 min-
 201 WO₃) films generate the highest photocurrents. In contrast, the longest anodization time (thickest
 202 film) yields a photoanode with very poor photocatalytic properties (**Fig. 1 (G-I) red lines**). The
 203 highly disordered structure of thicker films is not conducive to efficient charge transfer, and this
 204 reflects in the relatively poor photocatalytic activity of this film. Namely, 30min-WO₃ has a
 205 maximum $j_{ph} = 0.045 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$, while 2min-WO₃ films produce a maximum $j_{ph} = 0.46 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$.

206 An inverse effect was observed for r-WO₃ films (**Fig. 1 (G-I) blue lines**). The electrochemical
 207 reduction and activation treatment increased the photocatalytic activity of the 30min-r-WO₃ film over
 208 10 times, whereas the 2min-r-WO₃ film showed only a marginal improvement versus its as-anodized
 209 counterpart. After reduction water permeates into the film and protons intercalate into the near-
 210 surface WO₃, forming a H_xWO₃ hydrogen tungsten bronze (Reichman and Bard, 1979). This
 211 structure has been reported to be significantly more conductive than WO₃ (Whittingham, 2004; Xi et
 212 al., 2014). As the structure becomes more conductive photogenerated electrons reach the back
 213 contact faster; this results in faster photogenerated charge transfer kinetics in LSV and steady-state
 214 measurements. It is also likely that reduction decreases the number of defects that act as electron or
 215 hole traps in this material, thus increasing photon conversion efficiency (Liu et al., 2016). Both of
 216 these effects result in a much higher measured photocurrent for r-WO₃ films. The overall highest
 217 photocurrent was generated by the 5min-r-WO₃ film.

218 The potentiostatic curves that were obtained at 1.2 V in **Fig. 2A** show the behavior of measured
 219 current under constant illumination. A near-steady-state photocurrent for as-anodized WO₃ films is
 220 reached almost immediately, with the exception of 2min-WO₃, which reaches a maximum current
 221 after ~ 30 minutes. In contrast, for the reduced films the initial current decreases sharply until a
 222 minimum is reached after 60 – 300 s based on anodization time. Then the measured current densities
 223 begin to increase and only approach steady state after ~ 2 hours.

224

[FIGURE 2]

225 The anodic activation after the reduction step was performed because it had been noticed that it takes
 226 some time of potentiostatic illumination for the r-WO₃ films to approach a steady-state photocurrent.
 227 In the curves of **Fig. 2A** the background current was neglected. To illustrate the simultaneously
 228 occurring “dark” process, **Fig. 2B** presents a typical activation curve obtained for a 5min-r-WO₃ film
 229 at 1.2 V. Here constant illumination was interrupted by switching the LED off for 2 seconds every 60
 230 seconds. Thus the “UV off” parts of the curve reasonably represent the dark current. As the
 231 measurement begins the dark current starts at ~ 60 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ and drops to fewer than 10 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$ after
 232 1000 seconds. In contrast, j_{ph} (the difference between the *UV off* and *UV on* pulses) increases from ~
 233 0.12 mA cm^{-2} to 0.5 mA cm^{-2} (**Fig. 2B**). It is assumed that the increase in photocurrent during
 234 activation of reduced WO₃ films is not linked to background processes such as re-oxidation, which is
 235 attested by XPS analysis discussed below.

236 Potentiostatic UV on/off pulses at 1.2 V were applied in order to obtain information on $j_{t=0}$ (the
 237 instantaneous photocurrent) and j_{ss} (the steady-state photocurrent). The most rudimentary
 238 interpretation of a photocurrent pulse profile is that the difference between $j_{t=0}$ and j_{ss} is proportional
 239 to the amount of minority charge carriers that recombine at the semiconductor’s surface, i.e. transfer
 240 efficiency (Mokhtarimehr and Tatarkova, 2017). It is, however, evident that only the 2min-WO₃ (**Fig.**

241 **3A)** and 2min-r-WO₃ (**Fig. 3B**) films exhibit the initial “overshoot”. Even in this case j_{ss} is
 242 approached rapidly, and the difference can be effectively disregarded. The transfer and
 243 recombination kinetics will be further elucidated using non-stationary photoelectrochemical methods
 244 in *section 3.3*. The slight decrease of j_{ph} over the duration of the pulse also shows that the 2min-WO₃
 245 and 2min-r-WO₃ films are less photoelectrochemically stable. This could be caused by non-reversible
 246 electron-hole recombination and the depletion of the space charge layer, but it could also be related to
 247 electro- or photo-corrosion of the films under anodic conditions.

248

[FIGURE 3]

249 To investigate whether any structural changes occur in the material during reduction and activation,
 250 XPS spectra were registered for 5min-WO₃ films: as-anodized, just after reduction, and after
 251 reduction followed by an activation step as shown in **Fig. 2B**. The W4f core-level spectrum of an as-
 252 anodized film consists of two peaks at 38.1 eV and 36.0 eV (**Fig. 4A**). These peaks are fitted well by
 253 a doublet that corresponds to W⁶⁺ oxide (4f_{5/2} ~ 37.8 eV, 4f_{7/2} ~ 35.7 eV (Blackman and Parkin,
 254 2005; Yang et al., 2009; Li et al., 2010)), although a small shift towards higher binding energies is
 255 seen. Peak integration shows that 96.9% of the area belongs to the W⁶⁺ signal (**Table 2**). Fitting also
 256 reveals a small amount (3.1 %) of W⁵⁺ (4f_{5/2} 37.3 eV, 4f_{7/2} 35. eV / Δ B.E. 2.1 eV), for which similar
 257 binding energies were reported (Wang et al., 2012; Hu et al., 2021) . It is possible for W⁵⁺ to exist in
 258 the structure as a residual intermediate W₂O₅ left after anodization, but more likely this signal occurs
 259 due to the appearance of defect sites – oxygen-deficient W within the crystal lattice (Cheng et al.,
 260 2013). WO₃ is an n-type semiconductor where oxygen vacancies act as electron donor sites, and at
 261 the semiconductor/electrolyte interface exposed W⁵⁺ sites adsorb oxygen species and participate in
 262 the OER mechanism as active sites. Moreover, in the O1s spectrum (**Fig. 4B**) the peak at 531 eV
 263 deconvolutes into three binding states that have been attributed to O-W bonds (530.8 eV), O-
 264 vacancies (531.4 eV), and O-OH bonds (532.4 eV) (Vasilopoulou et al., 2014; Yu et al., 2017; Lee et
 265 al., 2018).

266 It is therefore all the more intriguing that after reduction the signal of W⁵⁺ grows substantially (**Fig.**
 267 **4C**). 18.3 % of the peak area can now be attributed to W⁵⁺ bonds and the signal of W⁶⁺ decreases
 268 correspondingly. Analysis of the respective O1s spectrum reveals a drop in O-W bonds (from 72.1 %
 269 before reduction to 55.4% after), and a double increase of the O-vacancy bond signal. Also, the O-
 270 OH signal had decreased, suggesting that the intercalated protons interact with exposed unsaturated
 271 W rather than O at the semiconductor/electrolyte interface. It has been suggested that electrochemical
 272 reduction of WO₃ results in the formation of tungsten bronzes with an approximate stoichiometry of
 273 H_xWO₃, and the results of this measurement agree with that.

274 Steady-state measurements showed that immediately after reduction the r-WO₃ films are poorly
 275 photoactive, but after an activation step, they typically generate several times larger photocurrents.
 276 **Fig. 4D** shows the W4f spectrum of an activated r-WO₃ film: it appears as an intermediate between
 277 plain WO₃ and fresh r-WO₃. The signal of W⁵⁺ had decreased, but the integrated peak area was still
 278 7.1% - over two times larger than for the WO₃ film. However, although the amount of W⁶⁺ had
 279 returned to near-initial levels, the O-vacancy signal remained elevated even after activation. This
 280 correlation between structure and photoactivity may be related to the emergence of an optimal
 281 amount of W⁵⁺ sites/oxygen vacancies. Too few vacancies (e.g., for plain WO₃) reduce the effect of
 282 them acting as electron donor dopants overall, resulting in poorer photoexcitation of charge carriers.
 283 Too many vacancies (as for fresh r-WO₃) act as electron traps, and promote recombination of
 284 photogenerated charge carriers. Then the mechanism of activation may be such: when a fresh r-WO₃
 285 film is illuminated, photogeneration and transfer of charge carriers begins. Recombination inevitably

286 occurs due to the increased number of W^{5+} trap sites, and the observed j_{ph} is relatively small. Over
287 time, as this process proceeds, non-reversible recombination results in the decrease of the number of
288 trap sites – this results in a larger j_{ph} , and corresponds to a weaker W^{5+} signal in the XPS spectrum of
289 an activated film. A small increase of the Na 1s signal was also observed after activation (0.18% to
290 0.55%), which may be a sign of anodic intercalation that has been documented to occur on bulk WO_3
291 (Szkoda et al., 2021). Therefore, electrochemical reduction, followed by activation, can possibly be
292 used to quite accurately tune the number of vacancies in WO_3 films.

293 [FIGURE 4]

294 [TABLE 2]

295 3.2 Photo electrochemical impedance study

296 Electrochemical impedance spectra were obtained with a constant light intensity of 50 mW cm^{-2} at
297 increasingly anodic applied potentials (0.4, 0.8, 1.2, 1.6, 2.0 V). A good understanding of the system
298 under investigation is crucial for interpretation of impedance spectra. It is evident from polarization
299 data (**Fig. 1**) that under dark conditions no Faradaic processes occur on WO_3 films, and the same is
300 assumed for the reduced and activated films. This means that charge carrier photoexcitation within
301 the space charge layer will decide the low frequency response of the PEIS spectra of this system.

302 A collection of representative PEIS spectra is presented in **Fig. 5**. From the Nyquist coordinates it is
303 apparent that the WO_3 impedance response draws a depressed semicircle in the complex plane. The
304 width of this semicircle is smallest for the most photoactive films (i.e., 2min- WO_3), and the
305 magnitude of the film's impedance increases with anodization time. Although the complex plane
306 seems to display one semicircle, a closer look at the Bode coordinates reveals that the response is in
307 fact comprised from two distinct time constants (**Fig. 5B**), which are only well distinguishable for
308 5min- WO_3 and 30min- WO_3 films. Only the low-frequency component could be extracted for the
309 2min- WO_3 film.

310 The electrochemical reduction and activation process seems to work by increasing the conductivity of
311 the films, as is confirmed by their PEIS spectra (**Fig. 5A and B insets**). The impedance magnitudes
312 of r- WO_3 decrease several times when compared to their respective as-anodized films.

313 As was the case with j_{ph} measurements, the effect is most significant for the least-photoactive 30min-
314 WO_3 film. It is also interesting to note that from the Bode spectra it appears that, while reduction has
315 little effect on the low frequency range, it strongly suppresses the high frequency response. In PEIS
316 high frequencies can often be attributed to capacitances caused by the charge/discharge of the double
317 layer and intermediate surface states. This may be an indication that the r- WO_3 material has more
318 favorable adsorption/desorption kinetics of OER intermediates because the high frequency response
319 is more in phase with the perturbation. In a typical full characterization of a film the PEIS spectra
320 were registered at incrementally increasing anodic potentials up to 2.0 V. LSV measurements had
321 shown that in this range j_{ph} grows with applied potential, but interestingly the system's impedance
322 also increases (**Fig. 6**). This means that the semiconductor material becomes less conductive even
323 though a higher generated photocurrent is observed. Technically, this behavior can be related to the
324 $j_{ph} - E$ curves that can be inferred from the "UV On" parts of **Fig. 1**.

325 [FIGURE 5]

326 A sharper rise in j_{ph} is observed at lower potentials, and the increase trends toward a plateau as the
 327 potential is further swept anodically. Because the PEIS response is generated by integrating a small
 328 part of the $j_{ph} - E$ curve under perturbation by a set potential amplitude, a steeper curve will result in
 329 more integrated current – a smaller impedance. These considerations can be further elaborated by
 330 applying equivalent circuit fitting.

331 The measured spectra were processed by fitting them to an equivalent electrical circuit (EC), where a
 332 single time constant is represented by an RC element with a capacitor connected in parallel to a
 333 resistor. Because two time constants are generally observed, the EC must have two RC elements.
 334 This results in an EC that is commonly used in electrochemical impedance modeling, and has been
 335 frequently applied to fit the spectra of photoanodes (**Fig. 6 inset**).

336 **[FIGURE 6]**

337 In this circuit R_s is the series resistance. CPE_{dl} is the double layer (Helmholtz) capacitance
 338 represented by a constant phase element to account for surface inhomogeneity, but it can overlap
 339 with a capacitance that is caused by the charge/discharge of surface states. R_{ct} is the associated
 340 charge transfer resistance. CPE_{sc} and R_{sc} are related to the semiconductor's space charge layer: CPE_{sc}
 341 should be proportional to the layer's width, provided that the depletion zone acts as an insulating
 342 layer. The nature of R_{sc} requires a deeper explanation. Broadly speaking, a resistance is a measure of
 343 the electrical force that a charge carrier must overcome in order to move through an electrical field of
 344 certain strength. R_{sc} may be thought of as the electrical resistance of the space charge layer between
 345 the point where a charge carrier is generated and where it exits the layer. When the photoanode is
 346 illuminated, a flux of holes (that is equal to the flux of incident photons multiplied by a conversion
 347 coefficient) begins moving in the direction of the semiconductor/electrolyte interface. Therefore, R_{sc}
 348 must be a measure of this flux. The circuit's parameters were plotted as a function of applied
 349 potential, and these trends were then compared to examine whether the increased photoactivity of r-
 350 WO_3 over plain films could be attributed to any of them. The results of an exemplary analysis are
 351 presented in **Fig. 7**.

352 **[FIGURE 7]**

353 Interesting tendencies are revealed when examining the space-charge-related components and their
 354 relation to the applied potential (**Fig. 7A**). The physical meaning of C_{sc} can be likened to the width of
 355 the space charge layer within an illuminated photoactive semiconductor. As the photogenerated
 356 charge carriers transfer away (e^- towards the back contact, and h^+ towards the electrolyte) an
 357 insulating depletion region forms, resulting in a measurable capacitance. As the depletion layer
 358 widens, the capacitance should decrease. The C_{sc} values for both WO_3 and reduced films decrease
 359 with applied potential, but generally C_{sc} of r- WO_3 films are larger, indicating smaller space charge
 360 layer widths. It must be pointed out that this interpretation assumes that the relative permittivity of
 361 the material remains constant, which may make the comparison less accurate.

362 On the other hand, R_{sc} values increase linearly with applied potential, reflecting the growing
 363 magnitude of the spectra in **Figure 6**. This is a peculiar observation, as it implies that the system is
 364 becoming less conductive while the steady-state photocurrent increases (**Fig. 7B**). $1/R_{sc}$, which
 365 should be in some way representative of photogenerated charge carrier transfer, drops with applied
 366 potential in stark contrast with the increasing steady-state photocurrent. If the incident photon flux is
 367 constant, and bias potential is increased (i.e., the space charge layer expands), the photogenerated
 368 charge carrier flux should also increase. All this points towards that R_{sc} is not a direct measure of the

369 flux. Instead, it is related to the change of the flux over bias potential $-\Delta\phi_{h+}/\Delta E$. Values of j_{ss} that
370 had been obtained from steady state UV pulse measurements were used to calculate the rudimentary
371 derivative values of $\Delta j_{ss}/\Delta E$, which are presented as a function of applied potential in **Fig. 7B**. It can
372 be seen that, although experimental errors could have distorted the results, the same decreasing trend
373 is observed. Moreover, this relation between the charge carrier flux and applied electric field strength
374 is effectively photoconductivity as measured in $\text{mA V}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$. It then follows that this decrease in
375 photoconductivity is what determines the R_{sc} parameter.

376 The physical cause of this phenomenon can be traced to the balance between the expanding space
377 charge layer and decreasing charge carrier density. If C_{sc} can be considered a reasonable
378 approximation of the capacitance of the space charge layer, then its width W should be proportional
379 to $1/C_{sc}$ as per the parallel plate capacitor equation. If the relative permittivity ϵ_r were to be known,
380 the width of the depletion zone could be calculated. The ϵ_r of WO_3 is known to vary based on
381 electrodeposition conditions, but for illustration purposes a value of 33.3 (obtained for WO_3 films
382 formed by anodization in 0.3 M oxalic acid (Levinas et al., 2017)) will be considered. Then the width
383 and volume of the space charge layer is calculated, and the values of charge carrier density are
384 presented as a function of applied potential in **Fig. 7C**. It is evident that the charge carrier density
385 reaches a peak at a certain potential, which is ~ 1 V for the WO_3 film but closer to 1.2 V for r- WO_3 .
386 After this, the charge carrier density begins to decrease linearly as the space charge layer continues to
387 expand. It is also worth noting that this peak almost exactly corresponds to where the observed
388 steady state photocurrents intersect the calculated $1/R_{sc}$ trends in **Fig. 7B**. It may then be concluded
389 that the steady state photocurrent is equal to the photoconductivity when the hole density within the
390 space charge layer is at a maximum. Functionally, j_{ph} continues to rise with further increasing
391 potential, as its magnitude depends on the minority charge carrier flux rather than conductivity.

392 The origins and behavior of the high frequency components are more complicated to interpret. C_{dl}
393 should be caused by the charge and discharge of the Helmholtz double layer that forms at the
394 semiconductor/solution interface, so it is proportional to the electrochemically active surface area of
395 the electrode. However, it is sometimes noticed that in PEIS the Helmholtz capacitance is mixed with
396 a capacitance that arises from the dynamic surface charging by intermediate states (Fermín et al.,
397 1999). In **Fig. 7D** instead of recalculating CPE values capacitance they are presented as-modeled,
398 along with the n exponent of the CPE element. The values of CPE for WO_3 films are low and n drops
399 from 0.9 to 0.8 over the measured potential range, but for r- WO_3 n values begin at ~ 0.55 and rise
400 linearly to 0.87. This behavior seems to imply that on r- WO_3 films some surface diffusion of
401 intermediate states may occur at lower potentials. Moreover, the values of R_{ct} of the reduced film
402 were up to 40 times lower than those of the plain film.

403 **3.3 Intensity modulated photocurrent spectroscopy study (IMPS)**

404 IMPS was used to complement PEIS results, as it provides additional information on photon
405 conversion efficiency and hole transfer kinetics. The classic theory has been elucidated by
406 *Ponomarev* and *Peter* in their seminal work (Ponomarev and Peter, 1995), and textbook applications
407 have been excellently explained in multiple publications (Fermín et al., 1999; Klotz et al., 2016;
408 Zachäus et al., 2017; Antuch et al., 2018; Amano and Koga, 2020; Rodríguez-Gutiérrez et al., 2020)
409 which were taken into consideration when interpreting the obtained spectra. Initially, measurements
410 were carried out at 1.2 V and increasing light intensities (I_0 : 10 to 60 mW cm^{-2} at increments of 10
411 mW cm^{-2}). Under potentiostatic conditions the width of the space charge layer should remain
412 constant, as it is mostly dependent on the bias potential. According to the Gärtner equation (Gärtner,

413 1959) then the increase in j_{ph} should be related to the flux of photogenerated charge carries within the
 414 space charge layer, which is equal to the incident photon flux multiplied by a conversion coefficient.

415 The IMPS spectra shown in **Fig. 8** exhibit some unique characteristics. For one, the spectra begin in
 416 the third quadrant of the complex coordinate plane. This is an experimental fact that has also been
 417 observed for Fe, Ti, and W oxides (Peat and Peter, 1987; Goossens, 1996; Rodríguez-Pérez et al.,
 418 2017), and its origin is the high-frequency charge/discharge of the double layer. For this reason, the
 419 high frequency time constant is often called the “cell” time constant, and it is the product of solution
 420 resistance and total cell capacitance ($\tau_s = R_s * C_{tot}$). All of the spectra then intercept the H' axis at 417
 421 Hz (at which the phase shift equals -90°), after which substantial low frequency semicircles begin. It
 422 is immediately apparent that there is no surface recombination at this applied potential – at low
 423 frequencies the spectra trend towards intercept with the H' axis as the phase nears 0. According to
 424 IMPS theory, the low frequency semicircle is expected to reach a maximum at a certain frequency
 425 which is equal to the sum of both transfer constants ($\omega_{LF} = k_{tr} + k_{rec}$). If no recombination is
 426 experimentally observed, then $k_{tr} \gg k_{rec}$, and $\omega_{LF} = k_{tr}$ (Ravishankar et al., 2019). That is to say, the
 427 entire IMPS response, comprised from two semicircles, will be confined to the fourth quadrant of the
 428 complex coordinate plane. This is almost exactly what is observed in the obtained spectra – the low
 429 frequency semicircle decreases in magnitude with increasing I_0 , while the high frequency response is
 430 not significantly altered by light intensity.

431 **[FIGURE 8]**

432 However, although they appear as semicircles, they could not be modeled with a single CPE element,
 433 likely due to interference from the high-frequency response. In order to better distinguish the signal
 434 that occurs due to hole transfer, the following procedure for processing IMPS spectra was adopted: a
 435 semicircular fitting with a simple $R_1(CPE-R_2)$ equivalent circuit was applied to the low-frequency
 436 response. From the obtained values an entire semicircle was simulated on the complex plane plot.
 437 The values of ω_{LF} and $H'_{\omega \rightarrow 0}$ were obtained from this simulated semicircle that corresponds to the
 438 low frequency response. Note that here the parameters of the equivalent circuit do not have a physical
 439 meaning as they would in EIS. These observations point to the conclusion that, much like in
 440 electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, if two time constants are different by enough magnitudes,
 441 non-stationary spectroscopy methods will allow the discernment of one or both of them. In this case
 442 τ_s is impossible to calculate, but τ_{LF} is. The validity of this approach is shown in **Fig. 9** by comparing
 443 various parameters that had been obtained from steady-state, PEIS, and IMPS experiments.

444 The steady-state photocurrent increases linearly with I_0 for both WO_3 and r- WO_3 films (**Fig. 9A**).
 445 This is the first indication as to the mechanism of water oxidation: it has been demonstrated that this
 446 behavior is related to whether the photoelectrochemical reaction occurs through direct or indirect (i.e.
 447 hydroxyl radical assisted) hole transfer (Villarreal et al., 2004; Mora-Seró et al., 2005). In this case, a
 448 linear relation of j_{ph} to the light intensity is an indication of direct hole transfer. From parallel PEIS
 449 experiments it was determined that at 1.2 V for a WO_3 film, $1/R_{sc}$ values are almost equal to the
 450 observed steady state photocurrent. Conversely, for the reduced electrode, $1/R_{sc}$ values were larger
 451 throughout (also as seen in **Fig. 7B**).

452 **[FIGURE 9]**

453 As was discussed earlier, R_{sc} is a measure of the semiconductor's conductivity owing to the
 454 photogenerated charge carrier flux. The potentiostatic mode keeps the strength of the electric field
 455 effectively constant, and therefore the changes in the charge carrier flux are directly related to the

456 increasing incident photon flux, as per the Gärtner equation. As the hole flux increases at a constant
 457 potential, the conductivity and $1/R_{sc}$ is observed to grow linearly with I_0 . The difference between j_{ph}
 458 and $1/R_{sc}$ then becomes even more remarkable: for the WO_3 films - a collected e^- results in one h^+
 459 joining the flux because $j_{ph} \approx 1/R_{sc}$, but for the r- WO_3 films a collected e^- yields ~ 1.41 to 1.49 h^+
 460 based on I_0 .

461 The second important parameter of IMPS spectra is the low-frequency intercept with the real axis.
 462 The real axis of an IMPS plot is fundamentally related to quantum efficiency, i.e., the ratio between
 463 the photogenerated current and the incident photon flux. The so-called external quantum efficiency
 464 (EQE, functionally identical to IPCE) is defined as:

$$EQE(\lambda) = \frac{j_e(\lambda)}{q\varphi(\lambda)} = \frac{j_e(\lambda)}{j_\varphi(\lambda)} \quad (7)$$

465 Here j_e is the collected electrical current, and j_φ is the spectral flux expressed in the units of current, q
 466 is the elementary charge. If an IMPS spectrum were to be normalized by assuming that the maximum
 467 observed value of the real axis H' equals 1, then the low frequency intercept with the real axis would
 468 give the transfer efficiency. However, if the spectrum were to be normalized by the incident photon
 469 flux or not normalized at all, then the low frequency intercept should be proportional to the EQE.

470 At low frequencies the collected current approaches steady state, thus, the low frequency intercept
 471 should be proportional to the IPCE values that were calculated from steady-state photocurrent
 472 measurements. Indeed, for the non-normalized H' spectra that were presented in **Fig. 8**, it is observed
 473 that $H'_{\omega \rightarrow 0}$ values decrease with I_0 with the similar tendency as for IPCE (**Fig. 9B**). However, these
 474 values are dimensionless and demonstrably cannot be equated to steady state photocurrent. Here the
 475 enhanced photon conversion efficiency of r- WO_3 films is again seen, as the intercept values of the
 476 reduced film are ~ 5 times larger than those of the WO_3 film.

477 Another observation was made when normalizing the presented $H'_{\omega \rightarrow 0}$ values by j_φ . The normalized
 478 $H'_{\omega \rightarrow 0} / j_\varphi$ values decreased by a power law that was not entirely proportional to IPCE (**Fig. 9C**). In
 479 fact, the only other parameter within the system that would exhibit such a trend with I_0 was R_{sc} ,
 480 obtained from parallel PEIS measurements under identical conditions. Of course, if $H'_{\omega \rightarrow 0} \sim j_{ss} / j_\varphi$,
 481 then $H'_{\omega \rightarrow 0} / j_\varphi$ will be proportional to $1/j_{ss}$ (which is directly related to R_{sc} as discussed earlier). These
 482 results are interesting, and they connect the various parameters obtained by PEIS and IMPS. In
 483 practice this means that while the low frequency intercept is proportional to conversion efficiency,
 484 the normalized intercept is more proportional to photoconductivity.

485 Finally, the transfer constants of both plain and reduced films were found to increase with I_0 in linear
 486 trends (**Fig. 9D**). The k_{tr} of the WO_3 film ranged from 27.3 s^{-1} to 125.3 s^{-1} , whereas for the r- WO_3
 487 film it was almost double at lower intensities from 62.8 s^{-1} to 143.8 s^{-1} . Thus, the conductivity of the
 488 reduced films is larger, and the injection of holes into the electrolyte occurs at a faster rate, resulting
 489 in overall enhanced photocatalytic water splitting properties.

490 The following conclusions have been made about applying IMPS analysis to these films:
 491 photocatalytic activity in terms of steady-state photocurrent is directly proportional to $1/R_{sc}$ that is
 492 obtainable by equivalent circuit fitting of PEIS spectra. Also, the low-frequency intercept $H'_{\omega \rightarrow 0}$ is
 493 proportional to EQE, and larger H' values correspond to enhanced photon conversion efficiencies.
 494 Further implementation of this analysis is shown in **Fig. 10A**. Here, the presented spectra had been

495 obtained at different bias potentials. A significant difference is observed for the low frequency
 496 intercept $H'_{\omega \rightarrow 0}$ – its values increase as the applied potential is raised towards more anodic values.
 497 Recalling the previous discussion, this must mean that better photon conversion efficiency is
 498 achieved at higher potentials. Conversely, ω_{LF} decreases, which is not apparent from the profile of the
 499 spectra, but will be discussed in more detail later on.

500 The IMPS spectra (obtained at 1.2 V) of films that had been formed by anodization for increasing
 501 times are particularly intriguing, and are presented in **Fig. 10B**, but without fitting. For the films that
 502 had been formed by shorter anodizing durations (2, 5 minutes) the high frequency response overlaps
 503 the low frequency signal, as a broad semicircle is observed in the first half of the spectrum. This
 504 complicates estimation of ω_{LF} , but modeling by simulation and extrapolation of the low frequency
 505 response yielded usable data in most cases. Designation of the low frequency extremum is a known
 506 issue in IMPS analysis, and this method may result in an over- or under-approximation, but it
 507 provides consistency of data acquisition.

508 Furthermore, these films may also exhibit some recombination as is signaled by the appearance of a
 509 trend toward low frequency semicircles in the first quadrant, but these recombination signals are
 510 negligible and have been disregarded from broader data analysis. The low frequency intercepts with
 511 the real axis show that 2min-WO₃ and 5min-WO₃ films reach better photon conversion efficiencies,
 512 which fall drastically when the anodization time is extended to 30 minutes. As expected, the r-WO₃
 513 films have larger low frequency intercept values owing to their enhanced conversion efficiencies.

514 **[FIGURE 10]**

515 The relation between applied potential and transfer kinetics/conversion efficiency must also be
 516 discussed. IMPS analysis shows that as bias potential is increased the photon conversion efficiency
 517 also increases, which is in agreement with steady state measurements. To illustrate these tendencies,
 518 as well as to compare WO₃ and r-WO₃ films, **Fig. 11** contains the values of low frequency intercepts
 519 with the real axis, as well as transfer rate constant values that were obtained directly from ω_{lf} . It is
 520 seen that $H'_{\omega \rightarrow 0}$ increase with applied potential, and the intercept values of reduced films are overall
 521 larger, showing better photon conversion efficiency and directly relating to the observed difference in
 522 steady state photocurrents. In contrast, here the transfer rate constants k_{tr} of the reduced film are
 523 smaller than that of the plain WO₃ film. Moreover, k_{tr} decrease steadily throughout the entire
 524 potential range. It has been suggested that this behavior can be related to the mechanism of oxygen
 525 evolution through either mobile or immobile intermediate surface states (Kandiel, 2020). If k_{tr}
 526 increases with applied potential it would suggest that oxygen evolution occurs through coupling of
 527 two adjacent oxygen-containing intermediates. Otherwise, the trend of k_{tr} would point towards a
 528 mechanism where oxygen evolution occurs through a single immobile active site which reacts with
 529 other photogenerated holes and adsorbed OH⁻ species. Then k_{tr} , obtained from IMPS, may be related
 530 to $j_{ph} - I_0$ measurements (as in **Fig. 9A**), which also give an indication as to whether hole transfer
 531 proceeds through indirect (mobile) or direct (immobile) steps. In this case the $k_{tr} - E$ and $j_{ph} - I_0$
 532 behavior of the films agree and strongly suggest that water oxidation proceeds through direct hole
 533 transfer.

534 **[FIGURE 11]**

535 **3.4 Revealing high-frequency recombination with IMPS**

536 Typically, when a WO_3 film is illuminated an instantaneous flux of photogenerated holes moves
537 toward the semiconductor/electrolyte interface. If there is surface recombination, then $j_{t=0}$ will be
538 larger than j_{ss} ($0 < j_{t=0}/j_{ss} < 1$), and a characteristic “overshoot” will be observed. In an ideal case, $j_{t=0}$
539 would equal j_{ss} , meaning all holes that arrive at the interface are transferred into the electrolyte.
540 Finally, it is also possible that $j_{t=0}$ be smaller than j_{ss} , as was observed for the 30min- WO_3 film (**Fig.**
541 **12 and insets**). Upon illumination the measured photocurrent grows slowly until the flux of electrons
542 arriving at the back contact reaches a maximum, and a small but distinguishable j_{ss} peak is seen in
543 steady-state curves. For the plain WO_3 film 0.04 mA cm^{-2} was reached within ~ 10 seconds of
544 illumination. This is obviously a negative characteristic, as it is indicative of slow charge transfer,
545 poor charge carrier separation, and short lifetime of photogenerated holes. However, it presents an
546 excellent opportunity to elucidate the effects of reduction on the photocatalytic properties of anodized
547 WO_3 films.

548

[FIGURE 12]

549 After reduction two substantial changes are seen: the maximum photocurrent is reached faster, in up
550 to 5 seconds, and it becomes ~ 10 times higher (0.46 mA cm^{-2}). As it was discussed earlier, the
551 morphology of 30min- WO_3 films is highly porous, which hinders charge transfer. Electrochemical
552 reduction increases the permittivity of the film by forming a conductive H_xWO_3 phase throughout the
553 porous structure on the surface that is exposed to the electrolyte. This explains faster charge transfer,
554 but not a larger photocurrent, because a larger photocurrent must be related to photogenerated charge
555 carrier generation or separation. Although, IMPS is usually used to discern low frequency near-
556 surface recombination, the spectra of these films had certain characteristics that seem to indicate a
557 signal inversion at high frequencies (**Fig. 13**, spectra presented without fitting). In particular, for
558 30min- WO_3 films the admittance modulus $|\text{H}|$ declines to a minimum in the 10 kHz – 1 kHz range
559 (**Fig. 13A**), and this coincides with a sign reversal of the phase (**Fig. 13B**). In Nyquist plots this
560 corresponded to the formation of a high frequency loop. The reduced film, however, had lost the
561 phase inversion and $|\text{H}|$ minimum. Also, these features were not observed for 5min- WO_3 films: the
562 admittance modulus rose steadily as the phase dropped to near 0 at 0.1 Hz.

563

[FIGURE 13]

564 It must be kept in mind that in IMPS the signal is related to photon conversion and not photocurrent.
565 Then the drop in $|\text{H}|$ must be indicative of decreasing conversion efficiency, which is most likely
566 caused by recombination of photogenerated charge carriers with “traps” or defects. Because this is
567 not low frequency recombination it occurs not near the semiconductor-electrolyte interface, but
568 deeper within the bulk of the material, likely as electrons initiate diffusion toward the back contact
569 during the initial stages of a light pulse. This can also be related to the steady-state photocurrents
570 shown in **Fig. 12**, where it takes 10 seconds for the photogenerated charge carrier flux of a WO_3 film
571 to approach steady-state due to their short life time. Because these features are absent from r- WO_3
572 IMPS spectra, it can be concluded that reduction also decreased the amount of photogenerated charge
573 carrier traps, and this results in a much higher photon conversion efficiency as can also be inferred
574 from $|\text{H}|$ values at near-steady-state. Furthermore, parallel PEIS measurements showed the R_{sc} of
575 these films to be $11.44 \text{ k}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ (30min- WO_3) and $3.485 \text{ k}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ (30min-r- WO_3): a 3.3 time increase
576 in conductivity after reduction, which corresponds well to the difference in charge transfer kinetics
577 seen in steady-state pulses.

578 Therefore, IMPS spectra can be used as a qualitative indicator of bulk charge transfer efficiency – a
579 decrease in admittance modulus and phase reversal seem to correspond to slow charge transfer
580 kinetics due to the recombination with defects in the material's structure.

581 **4 Conclusions**

582 Highly porous WO₃ films have been obtained by galvanostatic anodization from the electrolyte
583 containing F⁻ and H₂PO₂⁻. The films were synthesized dependently on anodization time, which was
584 varied up to 30 minutes. The FIB cross-sections revealed that their thickness increases with the
585 anodization time, and all films have a porous morphology both on the surface and within the layer.
586 XPS analysis showed that the as-anodized films are WO₃, with a small W⁵⁺ signal. The
587 photoelectrochemical performance for oxygen evolution assessed in an acidic Na₂SO₄ electrolyte,
588 reveals that the shorter anodization times (2 or 5 minutes) yield films with rather high photocatalytic
589 activity that could reach ~ 2 % photon conversion efficiency at 1.2 V under 50 mW cm⁻². However,
590 the photocurrent of these films would drop considerably over a 2-hour test period. Electrochemical
591 reduction (H⁺ intercalation and activation) was applied on the as-synthesized WO₃ films to overcome
592 this drawback; this led to improved stability and activity. A maximum IPCE of 4.35 % was
593 calculated for a reduced WO₃ film that had been obtained after 5 min. of anodization. XPS spectra
594 reveal that after H⁺ intercalation the films show a stronger W⁵⁺-O and O-vacancy signal. However,
595 after intercalation and activation, W⁵⁺ re-oxidizes, while the O-vacancy signal remains increased.
596 PEIS and IMPS measurements confirmed that the photo-conductivity of r-WO₃ was considerably
597 superior, owing to more effective photoexcited charge carrier generation/separation. Finally,
598 interpretation of the high frequency part of IMPS spectra suggests that reduction significantly
599 reduces charge carrier recombination within the material's bulk. Thus, an in-situ electrochemical
600 reduction and activation treatment enhances almost every aspect of the photocatalyst – charge carrier
601 photogeneration/separation, the kinetics of charge transfer, as well as rate of hole injection into the
602 electrolyte. The proposed approach unlocks the catalytic activity towards OER of promising
603 photoanodes.

604 **5 Author contributions**

605 The synthesis of the films, their SEM surface morphology and photoelectrochemical
606 characterizations were performed by RL, under the supervision of NT and HC. The XPS structural
607 characterization and modelling was performed by TM. Writing and original draft preparation by RL.
608 Review and editing performed by RL, NT, and HC.

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613 **7 Conflict of interest statement**

614 *The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial*
615 *relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.*

616

617 **8 References**

- 618 Ali, H., Ismail, N., Hegazy, A., and Mekewi, M. (2014). A novel photoelectrode from TiO₂-WO₃
619 nanoarrays grown on FTO for solar water splitting. *Electrochimica Acta* 150, 314–319.
620 doi:10.1016/j.electacta.2014.10.142.
- 621 Amano, F., and Koga, S. (2020). Influence of light intensity on the steady-state kinetics in tungsten
622 trioxide particulate photoanode studied by intensity-modulated photocurrent spectroscopy.
623 *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry* 860, 113891. doi:10.1016/j.jelechem.2020.113891.
- 624 Antuch, M., Millet, P., Iwase, A., and Kudo, A. (2018). The role of surface states during photocurrent
625 switching: Intensity modulated photocurrent spectroscopy analysis of BiVO₄
626 photoelectrodes. *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental* 237, 401–408.
627 doi:10.1016/j.apcatb.2018.05.011.
- 628 Bak, T., Nowotny, J., Rekas, M., and Sorrell, C. C. (2002). Photo-electrochemical hydrogen
629 generation from water using solar energy. Materials-related aspects. *International Journal of*
630 *Hydrogen Energy* 27, 991–1022. doi:10.1016/S0360-3199(02)00022-8.
- 631 Blackman, C. S., and Parkin, I. P. (2005). Atmospheric Pressure Chemical Vapor Deposition of
632 Crystalline Monoclinic WO₃ and WO_{3-x} Thin Films from Reaction of WCl₆ with O-
633 Containing Solvents and Their Photochromic and Electrochromic Properties. *Chem. Mater.*
634 17, 1583–1590. doi:10.1021/cm0403816.
- 635 Calero, S. J., Ortiz, P., Oñate, A. F., and Cortés, M. T. (2016). Effect of proton intercalation on
636 photo-activity of WO₃ anodes for water splitting. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*
637 41, 4922–4930. doi:10.1016/j.ijhydene.2015.12.155.
- 638 Cao, J., Gao, Z., Wang, C., Muzammal, H. M., Wang, W., Gu, Q., et al. (2020). Morphology
639 evolution of the anodized tin oxide film during early formation stages at relatively high
640 constant potential. *Surface and Coatings Technology* 388, 125592.
641 doi:10.1016/j.surfcoat.2020.125592.
- 642 Casado, C., Mesones, S., Adán, C., and Marugán, J. (2019). Comparing potentiostatic and
643 galvanostatic anodization of titanium membranes for hybrid photocatalytic/microfiltration
644 processes. *Applied Catalysis A: General* 578, 40–52. doi:10.1016/j.apcata.2019.03.024.
- 645 Cheng, L., Hou, Y., Zhang, B., Yang, S., Guo, J. W., Wu, L., et al. (2013). Hydrogen-treated
646 commercial WO₃ as an efficient electrocatalyst for triiodide reduction in dye-sensitized solar
647 cells. *Chem. Commun.* 49, 5945. doi:10.1039/c3cc42206b.
- 648 Chu, Y., Yu, G., Hu, B., Dong, Q., Zhang, J., and Zhang, X. (2014). Effect of hypophosphite on
649 electrodeposition of graphite@ copper powders. *Advanced Powder Technology* 25, 477–482.
650 doi:10.1016/j.apt.2013.07.003.
- 651 Dong, C., Zhao, R., Yao, L., Ran, Y., Zhang, X., and Wang, Y. (2020). A review on WO₃ based gas
652 sensors: Morphology control and enhanced sensing properties. *Journal of Alloys and*
653 *Compounds* 820, 153194. doi:10.1016/j.jallcom.2019.153194.
- 654 Fermín, D. J., Ponomarev, E. A., and Peter, L. M. (1999). A kinetic study of CdS photocorrosion by
655 intensity modulated photocurrent and photoelectrochemical impedance spectroscopy. *Journal*
656 *of Electroanalytical Chemistry* 473, 192–203. doi:10.1016/S0022-0728(99)00109-6.

- 657 Fernández-Domene, R. M., Sánchez-Tovar, R., Lucas-Granados, B., Roselló-Márquez, G., and
658 García-Antón, J. (2017). A simple method to fabricate high-performance nanostructured WO
659 3 photocatalysts with adjusted morphology in the presence of complexing agents. *Materials*
660 & *Design* 116, 160–170. doi:10.1016/j.matdes.2016.12.016.
- 661 Gan, X., Zhou, K., Hu, W., and Zhang, D. (2012). Role of additives in electroless copper plating
662 using hypophosphite as reducing agent. *Surface and Coatings Technology* 206, 3405–3409.
663 doi:10.1016/j.surfcoat.2012.02.006.
- 664 Gärtner, W. W. (1959). Depletion-Layer Photoeffects in Semiconductors. *Phys. Rev.* 116, 84–87.
665 doi:10.1103/PhysRev.116.84.
- 666 Goossens, A. (1996). Intensity-modulated photocurrent spectroscopy of thin anodic films on
667 titanium. *Surface Science*, 10.
- 668 Gullapalli, S. K., Vemuri, R. S., and Ramana, C. V. (2010). Structural transformation induced
669 changes in the optical properties of nanocrystalline tungsten oxide thin films. *Appl. Phys.*
670 *Let.* 96, 171903. doi:10.1063/1.3421540.
- 671 Hu, Y., Hao, L., Zhang, Y., Ping, X., Liu, T., Zhao, Q., et al. (2021). Defect concentration regulation
672 in nanoflower-like WO₃ film and its influence on photocatalytic activity. *J Mater Sci: Mater*
673 *Electron.* doi:10.1007/s10854-021-05605-2.
- 674 Huang, Z.-F., Song, J., Pan, L., Zhang, X., Wang, L., and Zou, J.-J. (2015). Tungsten Oxides for
675 Photocatalysis, Electrochemistry, and Phototherapy. *Adv. Mater.* 27, 5309–5327.
676 doi:10.1002/adma.201501217.
- 677 Kandiel, T. A. (2020). Mechanistic investigation of water oxidation on hematite photoanodes using
678 intensity-modulated photocurrent spectroscopy. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology*
679 *A: Chemistry* 403, 112825. doi:10.1016/j.jphotochem.2020.112825.
- 680 Karastoyanov, V., and Bojinov, M. (2008). Anodic oxidation of tungsten in sulphuric acid solution—
681 Influence of hydrofluoric acid addition. *Materials Chemistry and Physics* 112, 702–710.
682 doi:10.1016/j.matchemphys.2008.06.029.
- 683 Klotz, D., Ellis, D. S., Dotan, H., and Rothschild, A. (2016). Empirical in operando analysis of the
684 charge carrier dynamics in hematite photoanodes by PEIS, IMPS and IMVS. *Phys. Chem.*
685 *Chem. Phys.* 18, 23438–23457. doi:10.1039/C6CP04683E.
- 686 Kwong, W. L., Savvides, N., and Sorrell, C. C. (2012). Electrodeposited nanostructured WO₃ thin
687 films for photoelectrochemical applications. *Electrochimica Acta* 75, 371–380.
688 doi:10.1016/j.electacta.2012.05.019.
- 689 Lai, C. W., and Sreekantan, S. (2013). Fabrication of WO₃ nanostructures by anodization method for
690 visible-light driven water splitting and photodegradation of methyl orange. *Materials Science*
691 *in Semiconductor Processing* 16, 303–310. doi:10.1016/j.mssp.2012.10.007.
- 692 Lee, S. Y., Shim, G., Park, J., and Seo, H. (2018). Tunable polaron-induced coloration of tungsten
693 oxide via a multi-step control of the physicochemical property for the detection of gaseous F.
694 *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 20, 16932–16938. doi:10.1039/C8CP00158H.

- 695 Levinas, R., Tsyntaru, N., Lelis, M., and Cesiulis, H. (2017). Synthesis, electrochemical impedance
696 spectroscopy study and photoelectrochemical behaviour of as-deposited and annealed WO₃
697 films. *Electrochimica Acta* 225, 29–38. doi:10.1016/j.electacta.2016.12.112.
- 698 Li, W., Li, J., Wang, X., Luo, S., Xiao, J., and Chen, Q. (2010). Visible light photoelectrochemical
699 responsiveness of self-organized nanoporous WO₃ films. *Electrochimica Acta* 56, 620–625.
700 doi:10.1016/j.electacta.2010.06.025.
- 701 Li, Y., Tang, Z., Zhang, J., and Zhang, Z. (2017). Enhanced photocatalytic performance of tungsten
702 oxide through tuning exposed facets and introducing oxygen vacancies. *Journal of Alloys and
703 Compounds* 708, 358–366. doi:10.1016/j.jallcom.2017.03.046.
- 704 Lin, L., Cheng, C.-P., and Teng, T.-P. (2016). Electrodeposition-Based Fabrication and
705 Characteristics of Tungsten Trioxide Thin Film. *Journal of Nanomaterials* 2016, 1–12.
706 doi:10.1155/2016/3623547.
- 707 Liu, X., Wang, F., and Wang, Q. (2012). Nanostructure-based WO₃ photoanodes for
708 photoelectrochemical water splitting. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 14, 7894.
709 doi:10.1039/c2cp40976c.
- 710 Liu, Y., Li, J., Li, W., He, H., Yang, Y., Li, Y., et al. (2016). Electrochemical Doping Induced In Situ
711 Homo-species for Enhanced Photoelectrochemical Performance on WO₃ Nanoparticles Film
712 Photoelectrodes. *Electrochimica Acta* 210, 251–260. doi:10.1016/j.electacta.2016.05.165.
- 713 Macdonald, D. D., Biaggio, S. R., and Song, H. (1992). Steady-State Passive Films: Interfacial
714 Kinetic Effects and Diagnostic Criteria. *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 139, 170–177.
715 doi:10.1149/1.2069165.
- 716 Manovah David, T., Wilson, P., Ramesh, C., and Sagayaraj, P. (2014). A comparative study on the
717 morphological features of highly ordered titania nanotube arrays prepared via galvanostatic
718 and potentiostatic modes. *Current Applied Physics* 14, 868–875.
719 doi:10.1016/j.cap.2014.04.002.
- 720 Mardare, C. C., and Hassel, A. W. (2019). Review on the Versatility of Tungsten Oxide Coatings.
721 *Phys. Status Solidi A* 216, 1900047. doi:10.1002/pssa.201900047.
- 722 Mokhtarimehr, M., and Tatarkova, S. A. (2017). Photocurrent transients of thin-film solar cells. *J.*
723 *Opt. Soc. Am. B* 34, 1705. doi:10.1364/JOSAB.34.001705.
- 724 Mora-Seró, I., Villarreal, T. L., Bisquert, J., Pitarch, Á., Gómez, R., and Salvador, P. (2005).
725 Photoelectrochemical Behavior of Nanostructured TiO₂ Thin-Film Electrodes in Contact
726 with Aqueous Electrolytes Containing Dissolved Pollutants: A Model for Distinguishing
727 between Direct and Indirect Interfacial Hole Transfer from Photocurrent Measurements. *J.*
728 *Phys. Chem. B* 109, 3371–3380. doi:10.1021/jp045585o.
- 729 Mukherjee, N., Paulose, M., Varghese, O. K., Mor, G. K., and Grimes, C. A. (2003). Fabrication of
730 nanoporous tungsten oxide by galvanostatic anodization. *J. Mater. Res.* 18, 2296–2299.
731 doi:10.1557/JMR.2003.0321.

- 732 Ou, J. Z., Balendhran, S., Field, M. R., McCulloch, D. G., Zoofakar, A. S., Rani, R. A., et al. (2012).
733 The anodized crystalline WO₃ nanoporous network with enhanced electrochromic properties.
734 *Nanoscale* 4, 5980. doi:10.1039/c2nr31203d.
- 735 Parkhutik, V. P., and Shershulsky, V. I. (1992). Theoretical modelling of porous oxide growth on
736 aluminium. *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* 25, 1258–1263. doi:10.1088/0022-3727/25/8/017.
- 737 Patel, K. J., Panchal, C. J., Desai, M. S., and Mehta, P. K. (2010). An investigation of the insertion of
738 the cations H⁺, Na⁺, K⁺ on the electrochromic properties of the thermally evaporated WO₃
739 thin films grown at different substrate temperatures. *Materials Chemistry and Physics* 124,
740 884–890. doi:10.1016/j.matchemphys.2010.08.021.
- 741 Patel, K. J., Panchal, C. J., Kheraj, V. A., and Desai, M. S. (2009). Growth, structural, electrical and
742 optical properties of the thermally evaporated tungsten trioxide (WO₃) thin films. *Materials*
743 *Chemistry and Physics* 114, 475–478. doi:10.1016/j.matchemphys.2008.09.071.
- 744 Peat, R., and Peter, L. M. (1987). A study of the passive film on iron by intensity modulated
745 photocurrent spectroscopy. *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry and Interfacial*
746 *Electrochemistry* 228, 351–364. doi:10.1016/0022-0728(87)80117-1.
- 747 Ponomarev, E. A., and Peter, L. M. (1995). A generalized theory of intensity modulated photocurrent
748 spectroscopy (IMPS). *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry* 396, 219–226.
749 doi:10.1016/0022-0728(95)04115-5.
- 750 Qi, H., Wolfe, J., Wang, D., Fan, H. J., Fichou, D., and Chen, Z. (2014). Triple-layered
751 nanostructured WO₃ photoanodes with enhanced photocurrent generation and superior
752 stability for photoelectrochemical solar energy conversion. *Nanoscale* 6, 13457–13462.
753 doi:10.1039/C4NR03982C.
- 754 Ravishankar, S., Riquelme, A., Sarkar, S. K., Garcia-Batlle, M., Garcia-Belmonte, G., and Bisquert,
755 J. (2019). Intensity-Modulated Photocurrent Spectroscopy and Its Application to Perovskite
756 Solar Cells. *J. Phys. Chem. C* 123, 24995–25014. doi:10.1021/acs.jpcc.9b07434.
- 757 Reichman, B., and Bard, A. J. (1979). The Electrochromic Process at WO₃ Electrodes Prepared by
758 Vacuum Evaporation and Anodic Oxidation of W. *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 126, 583–591.
759 doi:10.1149/1.2129091.
- 760 Rodríguez-Gutiérrez, I., Djabatoubaï, E., Su, J., Vega-Poot, A., Rodríguez-Gattorno, G., Souza, F. L., et
761 al. (2020). An intensity-modulated photocurrent spectroscopy study of the charge carrier
762 dynamics of WO₃/BiVO₄ heterojunction systems. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*
763 208, 110378. doi:10.1016/j.solmat.2019.110378.
- 764 Rodríguez-Pérez, M., Rodríguez-Gutiérrez, I., Vega-Poot, A., García-Rodríguez, R., Rodríguez-
765 Gattorno, G., and Oskam, G. (2017). Charge transfer and recombination kinetics at WO₃ for
766 photoelectrochemical water oxidation. *Electrochimica Acta* 258, 900–908.
767 doi:10.1016/j.electacta.2017.11.140.
- 768 Santos, L., Neto, J. P., Crespo, A., Baião, P., Barquinha, P., Pereira, L., et al. (2015).
769 “Electrodeposition of WO₃ Nanoparticles for Sensing Applications,” in *Electroplating of*
770 *Nanostructures*, ed. M. Aliofkhaezrai (InTech). doi:10.5772/61216.

- 771 Solarska, R., Alexander, B. D., Braun, A., Jurczakowski, R., Fortunato, G., Stiefel, M., et al. (2010).
772 Tailoring the morphology of WO₃ films with substitutional cation doping: Effect on the
773 photoelectrochemical properties. *Electrochimica Acta* 55, 7780–7787.
774 doi:10.1016/j.electacta.2009.12.016.
- 775 Syrek, K., Zaraska, L., Zych, M., and Sulka, G. D. (2018). The effect of anodization conditions on
776 the morphology of porous tungsten oxide layers formed in aqueous solution. *Journal of*
777 *Electroanalytical Chemistry* 829, 106–115. doi:10.1016/j.jelechem.2018.09.054.
- 778 Szkoda, M., Trzcíński, K., Trykowski, G., Łapiński, M., and Lisowska-Oleksiak, A. (2021).
779 Influence of alkali metal cations on the photoactivity of crystalline and exfoliated amorphous
780 WO₃ – photointercalation phenomenon. *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental* 298, 120527.
781 doi:10.1016/j.apcatb.2021.120527.
- 782 Vasilopoulou, M., Soutati, A., Georgiadou, D. G., Stergiopoulos, T., Palilis, L. C., Kennou, S., et al.
783 (2014). Hydrogenated under-stoichiometric tungsten oxide anode interlayers for efficient and
784 stable organic photovoltaics. *J. Mater. Chem. A* 2, 1738–1749. doi:10.1039/C3TA13975A.
- 785 Vemuri, R. S., Bharathi, K. K., Gullapalli, S. K., and Ramana, C. V. (2010). Effect of Structure and
786 Size on the Electrical Properties of Nanocrystalline WO₃ Films. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*
787 2, 2623–2628. doi:10.1021/am1004514.
- 788 Villarreal, T. L., Gómez, R., Neumann-Spallart, M., Alonso-Vante, N., and Salvador, P. (2004).
789 Semiconductor Photooxidation of Pollutants Dissolved in Water: A Kinetic Model for
790 Distinguishing between Direct and Indirect Interfacial Hole Transfer. I. Photoelectrochemical
791 Experiments with Polycrystalline Anatase Electrodes under Current Doubling and Absence of
792 Recombination. *J. Phys. Chem. B* 108, 15172–15181. doi:10.1021/jp049447a.
- 793 Wang, G., Ling, Y., Wang, H., Yang, X., Wang, C., Zhang, J. Z., et al. (2012). Hydrogen-treated
794 WO₃ nanoflakes show enhanced photostability. *Energy Environ. Sci.* 5, 6180.
795 doi:10.1039/c2ee03158b.
- 796 Whittingham, M. (2004). Hydrogen motion in oxides: from insulators to bronzes. *Solid State Ionics*
797 168, 255–263. doi:10.1016/j.ssi.2003.08.056.
- 798 Wu, C.-M., Naseem, S., Chou, M.-H., Wang, J.-H., and Jian, Y.-Q. (2019). Recent Advances in
799 Tungsten-Oxide-Based Materials and Their Applications. *Front. Mater.* 6, 49.
800 doi:10.3389/fmats.2019.00049.
- 801 Xi, Y., Zhang, Q., and Cheng, H. (2014). Mechanism of Hydrogen Spillover on WO₃ (001) and
802 Formation of H_xWO₃ (x = 0.125, 0.25, 0.375, and 0.5). *J. Phys. Chem. C* 118, 494–501.
803 doi:10.1021/jp410244c.
- 804 Yang, F., Yang, B., Lu, B., Huang, L., Xu, S., and Zhou, S. (2006). Electrochemical Study on
805 Electroless Copper Plating Using Sodium Hypophosphite as Reductant. *Acta Physico-*
806 *Chimica Sinica* 22, 1317–1321. doi:10.1016/S1872-1508(06)60065-X.
- 807 Yang, M., Shrestha, N. K., and Schmuki, P. (2009). Thick porous tungsten trioxide films by
808 anodization of tungsten in fluoride containing phosphoric acid electrolyte. *Electrochemistry*
809 *Communications* 11, 1908–1911. doi:10.1016/j.elecom.2009.08.014.

- 810 Yu, S. Q., Ling, Y. H., Zhang, J., Qin, F., and Zhang, Z. J. (2017). Efficient photoelectrochemical
811 water splitting and impedance analysis of WO_{3-x} nanoflake electrodes. *International*
812 *Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 42, 20879–20887. doi:10.1016/j.ijhydene.2017.01.177.
- 813 Zachäus, C., Abdi, F. F., Peter, L. M., and van de Krol, R. (2017). Photocurrent of BiVO₄ is limited
814 by surface recombination, not surface catalysis. *Chem. Sci.* 8, 3712–3719.
815 doi:10.1039/C7SC00363C.
- 816 Zhang, L., Wang, W., Sun, S., and Jiang, D. (2015). Near-infrared light photocatalysis with
817 metallic/semiconducting H_xWO₃/WO₃ nanoheterostructure in situ formed in mesoporous
818 template. *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental* 168–169, 9–13.
819 doi:10.1016/j.apcatb.2014.12.018.
- 820 Zheng, H., Ou, J. Z., Strano, M. S., Kaner, R. B., Mitchell, A., and Kalantar-zadeh, K. (2011).
821 Nanostructured Tungsten Oxide - Properties, Synthesis, and Applications. *Adv. Funct. Mater.*
822 21, 2175–2196. doi:10.1002/adfm.201002477.
- 823 Zhu, X., Liu, L., Song, Y., Jia, H., Yu, H., Xiao, X., et al. (2008). Oxygen evolution and porous
824 anodic alumina formation. *Materials Letters* 62, 4038–4040.
825 doi:10.1016/j.matlet.2008.05.062.
- 826 Zych, M., Syrek, K., Zaraska, L., and Sulka, G. D. (2020). Improving Photoelectrochemical
827 Properties of Anodic WO₃ Layers by Optimizing Electrosynthesis Conditions. *Molecules* 25,
828 2916. doi:10.3390/molecules25122916.

829 **Figure captions**

830 **Fig. 1.** SEM images of as-anodized WO₃ films: top view (A-C) and FIB cross-sections (D-F); and
831 chopped UV on/off linear sweep voltammetry scans (10 s ON / 10 s OFF at 2 mV s⁻¹) of WO₃ and r-
832 WO₃ films at I₀ = 50 mW cm⁻² (G-I).

833 **Fig. 2.** Potentiostatic steady-state photocurrent curves of WO₃ and r-WO₃ films (A); activation
834 process of a 5min-r-WO₃ film (B). Both dependencies were obtained at 1.2 V and I₀ = 50 mA cm⁻².

835 **Fig. 3.** Steady-state potentiostatic on/off photocurrent pulses of WO₃ films obtained after anodization
836 at 25 mA cm⁻² for the indicated amount of time: as-anodized (A); reduced and activated (B). All
837 dependencies were obtained at 1.2 V and I₀ = 50 mA cm⁻².

838 **Fig. 4.** High-resolution W4f and O1s XPS spectra and fitted peaks of 5min-WO₃ films: as-deposited
839 (A, B); after reduction at -0.5 V for 300 s (C, D); after reduction and activation at 1.2 V, I₀ = 50 mW
840 cm⁻², 3000 s. (E, F).

841 **Fig. 5.** PEIS spectra obtained at I₀ = 50 mW cm⁻² and 1.2 V in Nyquist (A) and Bode phase (B)
842 coordinates of WO₃ and r-WO₃ (insets) films that have been formed by anodizing for 2, 5, and 30
843 minutes. Solid lines show fits to the equivalent circuit in the inset of Fig. 6.

844 **Fig. 6.** PEIS spectra of 5min-WO₃ film in dependence on the anodic potential. Inset: the equivalent
845 circuit that was used for fitting.

846 **Fig. 7.** Results of the EIS fitting data for WO_3 (red lines) and r- WO_3 (blue lines) presented as trends
 847 over applied potential: the low frequency components C_{sc} and R_{sc} (A); steady state photocurrent and
 848 modeled R_{sc} (B); the calculated charge carrier density (C); the high frequency constant phase element
 849 components CPE_{dl} and n (D). Data are for 5 min. (A-C) and 30 min. (D) films.

850 **Fig. 8.** IMPS spectra obtained at 1.2 V in dependence on UV light intensities (10% modulation
 851 amplitude). Measured on 5min-r- WO_3 film. Dashed lines represent semicircle fits.

852 **Fig. 9.** Analysis data of the IMPS spectra for WO_3 (red lines) and r- WO_3 (blue lines) in dependence
 853 on applied illumination intensity: steady-state photocurrent and R_{sc}^{-1} (A); trends of the low frequency
 854 intercept with the real axis and IPCE (B); trends of the normalized low frequency intercept and R_{sc} ,
 855 obtained from PEIS data (C); transfer constants, obtained from IMPS (D). Data measured for 5min
 856 films, at 1.2 V.

857 **Fig. 10.** IMPS spectra obtained at $I_0 = 50 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$ and 1.2 V in dependence on: applied potential for
 858 5min-r- WO_3 films (A); anodization time for WO_3 and r- WO_3 films (B).

859 **Fig. 11.** Low frequency intercepts and transfer rate constants as a function of applied potential for
 860 5min- WO_3 (red curves) and 5min-r- WO_3 (blue curves) films.

861 **Fig. 12.** Photocurrent transients measured at 1.2 V and $I_0 = 50 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$ for 30min- WO_3 (red curve)
 862 and 30min-r- WO_3 (blue curve) films. Insets show close-up views of the initial moments of the light
 863 pulse.

864 **Fig. 13.** IMPS spectra obtained at $I_0 = 50 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$ and 1.2 V in Bode modulus (A) and Bode phase
 865 (B) coordinates for WO_3 (red curves) and r- WO_3 (blue curves) films.

866 TABLE 1

867

868 **Table 1.** The overview of investigated samples and their lab-codes.

Anodization time, min	Conditions	Lab-code	Reduction + Activation	Lab-code
2	1 M Na_2SO_4 + 75 mM NaF + 0.1 M NaH_2PO_2 25 mA cm^{-2}	2min- WO_3	-0.5 V, 300 s + 1.2 V, 50 mW cm^{-2} 3000 s	2min-r- WO_3
5		5min- WO_3		5min-r- WO_3
30		30min- WO_3		30min-r- WO_3

869

870

871 TABLE 2

872

873 **Table 2.** Ratios of W and O bonds in as-anodized and modified WO_3 films, obtained from integration
 874 of XPS peak areas.

Film	W4f		O1s		
	W ⁶⁺ , %	W ⁵⁺ , %	O-W, %	O-vacancy, %	O-OH, %
<i>5min-WO₃</i>	96.9	3.1	72.1	17.4	10.5
<i>5min-r-WO₃</i>	77.1	22.9	55.4	35.8	8.8
<i>Activated 5min-r-WO₃</i>	92.8	7.2	56.4	32.4	11.2

875

876

Figure 1.JPEG

Figure 2.JPEG

Figure 3.JPEG

Figure 4.JPEG

Figure 5.JPEG

Figure 6.JPEG

Figure 7.JPEG

Figure 8.JPEG

Figure 9.JPEG

Figure 10.JPEG

Figure 11.JPEG

Figure 12.JPEG

Figure 13.JPEG

